

O'SMIRLIK DAVRINING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI

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Tarix va filologiya kafedrası o'qituvchisi

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada davr o'smirlari psixologiyasi hamda o'smir bolalarda kechadigan psixologik o'zgarishlar, ularning rivojlanishiga ta'siri haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: O'smir, xarakter, psixologiya, o'qish, muloqot, jiddiy munosabat, do'stlik, o'z-o'zini anglash.

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ADOLESCENT PERIOD

Abstract. This article talks about the psychology of adolescents of the period and the psychological changes that occur in adolescents and their impact on their development.

Keywords: Teenager, character, psychology, study, communication, seriousness, friendship, self-awareness.

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ОСОБЕННОСТЬ ПОДРОСТКОВОГО ПЕРИОДА

Аннотация. В данной статье говорится о психологии подростков и психологических изменениях, происходящих у подростков, и их влиянии на их развитие.

Ключевые слова: Подросток, характер, психология, учёба, общение, серьёзное отношение, дружба, самосознание.

O'smirlik 10—11 yoshlardan 14—15 yoshlargacha bolgan davrni tashkil etadi. Hozirgi o'smirlar o'tmishdoshlariga nisbatan jismoniy, aqliy va siyosiy jihatdan birmuncha ustunlikka ega.

Ularda jinsiy yetilish, ijtimoiylashuv jarayoni, psixik o'sish oldinroq namoyon bo'lmoqda. Aksariyat o'quvchilarda o'smirlik yoshiga o'tish, asosan, 5-sinf dan boshlanadi. «Endi o'smir bola emas, biroq katta ham emas»- ayni shu ta'rif o'smirlik davrining muhim xarakterini bildiradi. O'smirlik bolalikdan kattalikka o'tish davri bo'lib, fiziologik va psixologik jismoniy jihatdan o'ziga xos xususiyatlari bilan xarakterlanadi. O'smirlik - bu inson hayotidagi muhim va qiyin bosqich, hayotning qolgan qismini ko'p jihatdan belgilaydigan tanlov vaqti. O'smirlik davri bolaning ijtimoiy faolligining jadal rivojlanishi va qayta tuzilishi bilan ajralib turadi. Bola hayotining barcha sohalarida kuchli siljishlar sodir bo'lmoqda, bu yoshni bolalikdan kamolotga "o'tish davri" deb bejiz aytishmagan. Kichik maktab davridan so'ng bola alohida olingan shaxs sifatida o'z-o'ziga munosabatini shakllantirish jarayonida asosan ikki bosqichni boshidan kechiradi. Bu bosqichlar o'smirlik yoshini ikki xil davrga — kichik o'smirlik davri va katta o'smirlik davrlariga to'g'ri keladi. Birinchi bosqichda o'smir o'zini «bola»lardan ajratib, endi o'zini kattalar olamiga mansubligini ta'kidlamogchidek boladi. Kattalar hayotiga kirishga qiziqish o'smirlarning asosiy xarakteristikalarini hisoblanadi.

Bu davr uchun kattalarning xatti-harakatlariga taqlid qilish va o'zining mana shu yarashmagan qiliqlariga tanqidiy baho bera olmaslik, uning katta yoshli kishilarga yaqin bolishi, yordam berayotgan bir guruh tengdoshlari bilan ortiq darajada bog'liq. O'smir yoshdagilarni ta'lim va tarbiya berish ishlarida uchraydigan ayrim qiyinchiliklar bu yoshdagi bolalarning psixik

rivojlanishi va xususiyatlarini ba'zan yetarli darajada bilmaslikdan yoki inkor qilishdan kelib chiqadi. Bu davrda o'smirlarning o'z shaxsiy fikrlari paydo bo'ladi. Ularda o'z qadr-qimmatlari haqidagi tushuncha kengayadi. Ilmiy psixologiyaning aniqlashi bo'yicha o'smirlarning psixik taraqqiyotini harakatga keltiruvchi kuchlar, ularning faoliyatlari bilan tug'iladigan extiyojlar bilan bu extiyojlarni qondirish imkoniyatlari o'rtasidagi dialektik qarama-qarshiliklarni yuzaga kelishi va bartaraf qilinishidan iboratdir.

O'smirlik davrida yetakchi faoliyat — bu o'qish, muloqot hamda mehnat faoliyatidir.

O'smirlik davri muloqotining asosiy vazifasi — bu do'stlik, o'rtoqlikdagi elementar normalarini aniqlash va egallashdir. O'smir o'z faoliyatini muayyan prinsip, e'tiqod va shaxsiy nuqtayi nazari asosida tashkil qila boshlaydi. O'smir shaxsini tarkib toptirishda uning atrof-muhitga, ijtimoiy hodisalarga, kishilarga munosabatini hisobga olish lozim. Psixologlar o'tkazgan tadqiqotlardan ko'rinadiki, o'smirlarning ko'pchiligi qat'iyatlilik, kamtarlik, mag'rurlik, samimiylik, dilkashlik kabi ma'naviy, axloqiy tushunchalarni to'g'ri anglaydilar.

Ularning turmush tajribasida fan asoslarini egallash natijasida barqaror e'tiqodiy va ilmiy dunyoqarash tarkib topadi, shular zaminida axloqiy ideallar yuzaga kela boshlaydi. O'smirlar muloqotining asosiy xususiyati shundan iboratki, u tola o'rtoqlik kodeksiga bo'ysunadi.

O'smirlarning o'z tengdoshlari bilan muloqotda bolishi g'oyat katta ahamiyatga egadir.

O'smirlar do'stlik, o'rtoqlik va o'zaro yordamlashuvni hamma narsadan yuqori qo'yadilar: ana shunday o'zaro munosabatlar, o'spirinlik yillarida ham davom eta beradi. O'smirning do'stlari bilan muloqoti ham o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega. Tengdosh bolalar bilan prinsipial tenglik holatidagi munosabatlar muhitiga nisbatan o'smirda alohida qiziqish boladi. Bu hoi o'smirda yuzaga keladigan shaxsiy kattalik hissining etik mazmuniga mos keladi. Kattalar bilan muloqotda bolish tengdoshlari bilan bolgan muloqotning o'rnini bosa olmaydi. O'smirlik yoshi bu aynan o'smir o'g'il-qizlarning va ularning ota-onasi uchun jiddiy sinovli davrdir. Bu davrga kelib o'smirlar ko'pincha ota-onalari bilan, maktabdagi o'qituvchilari bilan janjallashishadi, ular kattalar tomonidan ko'proq mustaqillikka va minimal nazoratga erishishga harakat qilishadi.

Maktabda o'qitiladigan fanlar o'smir uchun o'z taxminlarini yuzaga keltirish yoki tekshirish uchun sharoit bo'lib xizmat qiladi. J.Piajening ta'kidlashicha, "Ijtimoiy hayot uch narsaning ta'siri - til, mazmun, qoidalar asosida shakllantiriladi". Bu borada o'zlashtirilgan ijtimoiy munosabatlar o'z-o'zidan tafakkurning yangi imkoniyatlarini yaratadi. Ma'lumki, o'smirlik davrida o'smirning "meni" qaytadan shakllana boradi. Uning atrofida ayniqs, o'z-o'ziga bo'lgan munosabati, qiziqishlari, qadriyatlarini yo'nalishi keskin o'zgaradi. O'smir yoshdagi bolani birinchi galdagi intilishi, u o'zini endi kichkina bola emas, balki katta bolib qolganligini atrofida ishontirishdan iboratdir. Mustaqil ishlar qilishga uringan o'smir shunday qilishga haqqi borligiga o'zini-o'zi ishontiradi, chunki men endi "katta bo'lib qoldim" deb o'ylaydi.

Shuning uchun ham psixologlar "katta bolib qolganlik tuyg'usi" ni shaxsning o'smirlik yoshdagi eng asosiy yangilik sifatida talqin qiladilar. L.S.Vigotskiy o'smirlik davrida qiziqishlarining o'zgarishiga bog'liq ravishda ikki fazani (salbiy va ijobiy) ajratib ko'rsatgan.

Salbiy faza ilgarigi qiziqishlarining so'nishi va yangi dastlabki jinsiy qiziqishlarning paydo bolishi bilan bog'liq. Bunda quyidagi salbiy xulq-atvor ko'rinishlari namoyon boladi: ish qobiliyatining, o'zlashtirishining pasayishi, o'smirning qopolligi va yuqori qo'zg'aluvchanligi, uning o'zidan qoniqmasligi va xavotirlanish va boshqalar. Ijobiy faza keng, chuqur yangi

qiziqishlarining paydo bo'lishi bilan xarakterlanadi. O'smirda boshqalarning va o'zining psixologik kechinmalariga qiziqish paydo bo'ladi. O'smirlik davridagi inqiroz - o'smir kechinmalari, uning strukturasi, mazmunining qat'iy o'zgarishi, buzilishidir. Bu tabiiy holatdir, ammo bu davrda ota-onalar o'zlariga nisbatan hurmatsizlik bilan shug'ullanishlari kerak. Ya'ni bolani mustaqillikka intilishi bu normal holat ammo ota-ona baribir nazorat qilib borishi lozim.

Undagi salbiy hatti-harkatlarni, o'smirning xulq-atvori tobora muammoli bo'lib qoladigan vaziyatlarda, qiyin vaziyatni qo'ldan chiqmasdan oldin hal qilish muhimdir.

O'smiringa o'zini baholashning shaxsiy mezonlarini ishlab chiqishga, o'zini «ichdan» ko'rishga va o'z yutuqlarini baholashga, shaxsining kuchli tomonlariga suyanishga o'rgatmoq lozim. O'smirlik davrining oxiriga kelib kuchli o'z-o'zini anglash ro'y beradi. Kattalarning bahosiga taqlid qilish yo'qolib, o'z-o'zini tarbiyalash, o'z-o'zini ko'rsatish, o'z-o'zini tasdiqlatish, o'z-o'zini namoyon qilishga intilish kuchayadi. O'z-o'zini anglashning yangi darajasini shakllanishi (o'zi haqidagi tasavvur, Men konsepsiyasi) o'z imkoniyatlari va xususiyatlarini, o'zining boshqalarga o'xshashligi va betakrorligini, o'zini shaxs sifatida bilish ehtiyojidan kelib chiqadi. O'smirlarning o'zi bilan bogliq kechinmalari ko'pincha salbiy bo'ladi.

Bu o'smirning o'ziga «tashqaridan» qarashiga, kattalarning bahosi va tasavvurlari interiorizatsiyasi qilinishiga bog'liq.

O'smirlik davridagi qiyinchiliklar yuzaga kelishini oldini olishda ota-onalarga quyidagi vazifalarni qo'yish maqsadga muvofiqdir:

-farzandlarga e'tiborli bo'lish

-ular bilan do'stona muloqot yaratish -qiziqishlarini inobatga olgan holda tarbiyasiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatmasligini nazorat qilish va sharoit yaratib berish

-o'smir yoshidagi bolalarga yetarlicha vaqt ajratish va ularning ko'proq kitob o'qishiga, ya'ni ta'lim jarayonlariga bee'tibor bo'lmaslik

-OAV lardan ma'lum vaqtda va muayyan bir tartib asosida foydalanishlarini nazorat qilib borish va yuqoridagi barcha jarayonlarni to'g'ri amalga oshishini taminlashdan iborat. Maktab amaliyotchi psixologlari uchun tavsiyalar:

-har bir yosh davrining o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini inobatga olgan holda ularni qiziqqan sohalarga yo'naltirish;

-o'quv jarayonidagi nafaqat o'smirlar psixologiyasiga balki boshqa bolalar tarbiyasiga ham birdek e'tiborli bo'lish;

-o'smir yoshidagi o'quvchilarning ota-onalari va maktab jamoasidagi boshqa o'qituvchilar o'rtasidagi hamkorlikni tashkil etish;

-o'smirlardagi o'zgarishlarni doimiy nazorat qilish uchun turli xil metodikalarni tartib bilan qollay olish;

-o'smirning tengdoshlar davrasidagi muloqot jarayonini chetdan kuzatib borish;

-bolalar bilan ularning qalbiga yol topa oladigan o'zaro hurmat va ishonch muhitini yaratishlari lozim.

Aynan yuqorida keltirilgan tavsiyalar o'z vaqtida va to'liq bajarilsa o'smirlikda yuzaga keladigan qiyinchiliklarning va ularning kelib chiqish sabablarini bartaraf etishga yordam beradi deb o'ylaymiz. O'smirlik davrining to'g'ri tashkil etilishi qolgan yosh davrlardagi muammolarga ham bee'tibor bo'lmaslikdan dalolat beradi.

O'smirlik – bolalikdan kattalikka o'tish davri bo'lib, fiziologik va psixologik jihatdan o'ziga xos xususiyatlari bilan xarakterlanadi va bu davrda o'smir tarbiyasiga e'tibor qaratish va bu tarbiya jarayonidagi qiynchiliklarga yuzaki qaramaslikni taqozo etadi.

O'smirlardagi asosiy o'zgarishni nimalar tashkil etadi? O'smir o'zini asta – sekin katta odam deb qis qila boshlaydi, lekin ko'p odat va xususiyatlari bolalarcha bo'lib qoladi. Bu hissiyot kattalik hissi deb ataladi va o'smirlikda asosiy psixologik yangilikdir. Bu his o'smirda o'ziga, atrofga muhitga, odamlarga nisbatan yangi hissiy pozitsiyani yuzaga keltiradi. U bolalar xulq-atvorini kattalar xulqi va qadriyatlariga qayta orientatsiya qila boshlaydi. O'smir o'z huquqlari doirasini kengaytiradi, kattalarni esa cheklashni xohlaydi.

O'smirlik yoshiga yetganda bolalarda burch va javobgarlik tuyg'ulari yetarli darajada o'sgan bo'ladi. Bolalar o'zlari ongli ravishda tanlagan qobil bo'lib qoladi. Mana shu davrda kattalar bolalarga «bemalol ish topshirishni ishonadilar» o'smirlarni oilada «kichkina» deb hisoblamay ulardan xo'jalik ishlariga yordam berish topshirilgan ishga javob berishni talab qiladilar. Ular bilan maslahatlashadilar ba'zi o'smilar ayniqsa ular o'rta maktab yoshining oxiriga borganda hatto o'ziga yaqinlarini qo'llovchi va tayanchi bo'lib qoladilar.

Xulosa. O'smirlarga ta'lim-tarbiya berishning yangi to'g'ri usullari hamda vositalarni topishi uchun o'smirlik yoshining o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini jismoniy va psixologik taraqqiyotini yaxshi bilishimiz kerak. Ularni his-tuyg'ularini hurmat qilish, muloqotda to'la tengdoshlik kodeksiga asoslanishini hisobga olgan holda ular bilan do'stona munosabatda bo'lish va nazoratni ham unutilib qo'ymaslik maqsadga muvofiqdir.

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